

Paths to execute Uniform Civil Code and its technical aspects

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Introduction :

Background : India is a highly diverse country, perhaps the most diverse country in the whole world. The four main religions in the world, Hinduism, Buddhism, Jainism and Sikhism originated from the Indian subcontinent. Christianity came to India in the 1st century AD. The major footprint of Islam's genesis can be traced down to the early 10th and 11th centuries. All these religions evolve contemporaneously, and the synthesis of all these religions is quite fascinating. Despite the amalgamation, every religion kept their certain traditions and customs intact. There are intermingling customs and rituals such as Hindus taking the purdah system from Muslims, while Muslims taking the dowry system from Hindus. But there are some traditions which were untouched. For Hindus, marriage is sacrosanct, it is purely divine while for Muslims marriage is a contract. In ancient India, Hindus were governed by the customs and traditions which are either orally passed down in

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generations or inspired by the various sources of written books such as Vedas, Puranas, or Smritis. In Manusmriti and the Yajnyawalkas Smritis, the codifications for Hindus are done in both civil and criminal matters. In Islam, primarily the Quran and Hadith state the rules for Muslims in civil and criminal matters. Jews and Christians are commanded by the Old Testament and New

Abstract

Uniform Civil Code(UCC Article 44).The code which has potential to stir the whole country. The code surges the emotions not only in the minority community(Muslims,Tribals) but also in the majority faction(Hindus). The process for the execution of code makes the legislators and judiciary take a deep dive into questions like, what should be the extent to which the state should interfere in personal matters. Civil matters such as marriage, divorce, inheritance, and maintenance are the main debatable subjects in this civil code as the laws regarding these subjects are different for different communities in India. The Muslim side opposes this code because they believe that, UCC will hamper their personal laws, and to oppose it, they wield the power of Articles 25 and 26 of the constitution. The party that wants UCC to be implemented in the country uses Articles 14, 15, 21 and 25 of the constitution. It is quite contradictory but it seems that the interpretation of Articles 25 and 26 is very important for the judiciary to pave the way for the legislators to enact the law. Enacting this code will bring uniformity in this country, but at the same time government and judiciary have to watch that pluralism and secularism should not be violated, as secularism and diversity of this country mark the basic structure of this constitution. The main question arises,"How will you execute the Uniform Civil Code and which paths you will follow to smoothen its procedure?" The paper is all about the probable procedures and technicalities that the judiciary and legislators have to follow while enacting this uniform code.

Testament respectively.

In the Hindu code bills, legislators define who are Hindus. It consists of Hindus, Buddhists, Jains and Sikhs. Mainstream Islam came to India in the 10th century, whereas Sikhism is a medieval phenomenon. Hinduism, Buddhism and Jainism evolved together since the 6th century BC, and though texts are different for these three religions they were bounded by Indian Civilizational impact. Rituals like Idol worship are forbidden in Buddhism and Jainism but in the course of time Hindu practices overtook Buddhism and Jainism. This is a civilizational impact. But this same civilizational impact also paved the way for diversity in customs and traditions. In North India, you can't marry in your

own 'Gotra', whereas in Maharashtra you can marry your maternal uncle's daughter who might belong to the same gotra. So basically there was a history in India, given the wide diversity there was no uniform code for Indian people, even not for Hindus who are the major community. The second largest faction has a different story to tell. Muslims were governed by the Shariat(a set of religious laws which includes Civil and Criminal matters). When the Mughals ruled India, Aurangzeb codified rules in a book called 'Fatwa i Alamgiri'. This was the Uniform law for all the Muslims in India. The interesting thing is, in terms of criminal matters this codified book was uniform to all the Indians. Hindus, Buddhists, Jains, Christians, Sikhs, Parsis, Jews and

Muslims, all have to follow the same rules, but in civil matters, there was no uniformity in laws.

The origin of the Uniform Civil Code can be traced back to the making of the Constitution. The architect of the Constitution B R. Ambedkar proclaimed many times the importance of having a Uniform Civil Code. During the country-making phase, opposition was ferocious to Ambedkar to have any such kind of uniformity in the law. Ambedkar stepped down as law minister as he wasn't able to convince the constituent assembly to have a Hindu code bill. But in the course of time and after the general election Pandit Jawaharlal Nehru emerged as an undisputed leader and with huge mandates in hand in both Lok Sabha and Rajyasabha, Pandit Nehru passed several laws (Hindu Marriage Act-1955, Hindu Succession Act 1956) to codify and reform Hindu personal laws. The codification was the culmination of the gradual evolution of Hindu personal laws which was started in 1829 when Sati-like practices were banned and the Hindu Widows Remarriage Act was passed in 1856 by Ishwar Chandra Vidyasagar. Britishers infiltrated in Hindus' personal arena but left Muslims' personal domain intact. In 1937, the Britishers enacted the Muslim Personal Law (Shariat) Application Act. This law basically sanctioned the age-old traditions of Sharia formally.

After the Independence when Hindu laws were codified uniformly in civil matter, there was an outcry from all the sections of the society to have a Uniform Civil Code for all citizens. Today the issues of marriage, maintenance, succession and adoption are basic contentious topics in this

debate regarding the Uniform Civil Code. Lawmakers as well as citizens are demanding the implementation of a Uniform Civil Code.

Existing Evidence

Literature Survey : Research paper of Rajeswari Sunder Rajan- Women between Community and State: Implications of the Uniform Civil Code Debates in India. Research paper of Nivedita Menon- A Uniform Civil Code in India: The State of the Debate in 2014. The lectures Dr. Vikas Divyakirti. Indian Constitution. Book by Rajiv Ahir-Spectrum. Polity by M. Laxmikant.

Research Gap : The problems regarding the execution and implementation of the Uniform Civil Code are vigorously debated. However, the paths and procedures that could be useful for the Uniform Civil Code are vague and not properly researched. The research is either too sociologically based or too emotive based. For the implementation of the Uniform Civil Code, a technical aspect is necessary. The law will be executed by proper interpretation of articles.

Objective

1. What are the paths and procedures for the implementation of the Uniform Civil Code?
2. Correct interpretation of Articles 15, 21, 25 and 26.
3. To study the two main factions of the Indian Society (Hindus and Muslims) regarding the implementation of the Uniform Civil Code.

Scope

The research is limited to the implementation process. Research will not grind the history or

future aspects of the law. The research will only focus on the current scenario and how can it be executed.

Methods

The qualitative research method is used for a better understanding of the topic. Materials such as research papers, books and YouTube videos are taken into consideration.

Results and Discussions

Hindu Code Bills were enacted in the 1950s and brought uniformity in Hindu personal laws. The Muslim Personal Law (Shariat) Application Act, was passed in 1937 and brought uniformity in Muslims' personal laws. Goa is the only state where the Uniform Civil Code is active in India. The code was executed in 1870 by the Portuguese. Uniform Civil Code means having uniformity in laws. Same law should be applicable to all the citizens of India across religion, gender, caste, race and place of birth. Article 15 states that, the state shall not discriminate against any citizen on grounds only of religion, race, caste, sex, place of birth, or any of them. The questionable issues in the Uniform Civil Code are marriage, maintenance, succession and adoption. These are the most personal themes in an individual's life which are inspired by the religion which he follows. Given the wide spectrum of diversity in India, every religious community in India follows the traditions and customs according to its religion which include marriage to adoption. Contradiction is, Hindus have the same law across all over India. He has to follow monogamy, give alimony(maintenance) to his wife, all her life(if she chooses not to marry again), and he

can adopt the child. Hindus can take the benefits of Hindu Undivided Family(HUF) where he doesn't have to pay taxes separately. These provisions meant these laws were only for the Hindus(here Hindus means, Hindu, Buddhist, Jain and Sikh). Here the catch is, that these are all personal matters, which are inspired by religion, and you can't discriminate against any citizen on the basis of religion, or gender. But on one side Hindu Code bills give benefits(Hindu Undivided Family tax benefits) that are not available to Muslims, Christians, Parsis and Jews. Later can't adopt any child just because by birth he/she is not Hindu. These are the discrimination based on religion. Muslim men can follow polygamy. He can have four wives. Muslim women have to follow Nikahhalala where you have to marry another person, consummate that relationship, then take divorce from him and then only she can marry her 1st husband who divorced her in the first place. Muslim men can marry a Muslim girl as soon as she hits puberty. These are some of the personal laws(Sharia) that Indian Muslims are following which are highly discriminatory according to article 15. Article 15 is being violated here as in the same marriage system Hindus, Buddhists, Jains and Sikh women are getting rights to go to the courts against discrimination but Muslim women don't. Indian Penal Code(IPC) was enacted in 1860 by the Britishers. IPC is Uniform across all over India. Every citizen is equal before the IPC. However, section 494 of IPC is not applicable to Muslims in India. Under Section 494 state can punish you if you marry without divorcing the 1st wife during her lifetime.

However, this punishment is not applicable to Muslims in India. Article 14 states, equality before the law, but here Indian Muslims are immune to the law. All India Muslim Personal Law Board considers themselves as a representative of the Indian Muslims in India. They don't want the state should infiltrate their personal laws. Their line of defence is Article 25. Article 25 guarantees the freedom of conscience, and the freedom to profess, practice, and propagate religion to all citizens. Muslim intelligentsia argue that Article 25 is their fundamental right and by virtue of the fundamental right they can profess and practice their religion the way they want. If the state is interfering in the personal laws then they are violating Article 15 because this article provides immunity from the state interference.

The supporters of the Uniform Civil Code want uniformity across India. They want section 494 should be applicable to Muslims. Along with political factions, there are numerous feminist organisations which work for the upliftment of women. One such organisation is Bhartiya Muslim MahilaAndolan formed in 2011 and led by ZakiaSoman. This means there is genuine concern for women's issues along with political motives and vote bank politics. Now the question is how will you execute the Uniform Civil Code in India.

1. What are the different paths and procedures for the implementation of the Uniform Civil Code?
2. What are the technical complications for the enactment of the Uniform Civil Code?
3. Concerning Issues of the two major

communities regarding the Uniform Civil Code.

The first way to implement a Uniform Civil Code is to have absolute Uniformity in the law. This is what most of the citizens wants in India. But this absoluteness is void. Forget about the inter-religious codes, even if they try to have uniformity in Hindu laws people have to face lots of difficulties. As mentioned earlier, in North India, Haryana and Rajasthan you can't marry in your own 'Gotra', whereas in Maharashtra you can marry your maternal uncle's daughter who might belong to the same Gotra. In Muslims, you can marry anyone with the exception of your own brother and sister. So how will you apply the uniform law in marriage for Hindus and at the same time for Muslims as well? The hurdles for the tribal communities are even greater. In northeast India, many tribes follow the matriarchal system. The Khasi tribe is the best example of this. How will you codify the maintenance codes and succession codes for the tribal communities when they have completely opposite system compared to the mainstream society which is patriarchal? So this path is very tough and full of technical obstacles.

The second way is to have a Uniform Code but with the exception regarding certain communities, places and genders. This seems to be a valid path, but again this path will dig its own grave in future. This exceptionalism evil is a very treacherous one. Lawmakers exclude Muslims while making the Hindu Code Bills. At that time there was a demand in parliament that, if we are reforming the Hindu personal laws, then why we are excluding the Muslim personal laws?

However Indian lawmakers gave exceptions to the Muslim faction. They thought the time was not right for this huge leap for the Muslim Community. Now even after more than 70 years, they are still following discriminatory laws. Today lawmakers will exclude certain factions and subjects in the law, but again in the future, the problem will arise as civilization is not stationary, it is dynamic. Customs and traditions change, and along with it comes a progressiveness that stimulates lawmakers to make more progressive laws. So this path is fallible.

The third path is the most well-suited and logical path. Let every community, faction have their own set of codes and laws. If some laws are discriminatory in nature then just change it to the better version or otherwise remove it completely. Hindu Code bills are the prime example of it. Lawmakers already proved that it can be done. The troublesome area is the Muslim community. Muslim community defended their stance regarding their personal laws on the basis of Article 25. However, Article 25 is not Absolute. Article 25 gives freedom of conscience, practice and profess of religion, which Muslims use as a whip to continue their Sharia Act, 1937. Article 25(1) and 25(2) does provide reasonable restrictions on Article 25 where the state can intervene. Article 25(1) provides four reasonable restrictions viz, public order, morality, health and the other provisions of this part. 'The other provisions of this part' mean Part 3 of the Indian Constitution which includes Fundamental Rights. This provision implies that the state can infiltrate Article 25 if

the practices in any religion is going against the other fundamental rights which includes Article 14, 15, and 21. Article 25(2)(b) states that, if a state wants to do social welfare and reforms, then the state can limit the power of Article 25. Article 25(2) also states when the matter comes to the secular aspects of the religion state can limit the influence of Article 25. Here secular aspect means, the things that are related to the religion, but interconnected to the much larger spectrum of society. For example, you can have the Azan in the masjid but the use of a loudspeaker can be banned by the state. Here Azan is an essential and integral part of Islam but the loudspeaker was nowhere mentioned in the Quran or Hadith. So the state can limit this practice on the basis of article 25(2) and no one can take the shoulder of article 25. This way a state can make the codification in the Muslim personal laws. The practice of polygamy was banned in many Muslim countries such as Turkey, Tunisia, Albania, and Kosovo and many Middle Eastern countries made many rules regarding polygamy, which makes this practice too rigid to follow. This implies that this is against morality and for social reforms state can remove it from the personal laws. The same should be said about Nikahhalala which is so gruesome process and is violation of the pride of women. So laws could be made in the Muslim Personal law without defying the constitution. It is the Constitution that gave our legislators the right to make laws against discriminatory traditions. Legislators did this before, that too 70 years ago with the Hindu personal laws. Hindus also opposed it and they also took shelter of Article 25. But by the sheer

will of Indian legislators, they removed the discriminatory traditions and customs in Hindu Personal Laws (Polygamy, child marriage, dowry etc.). So this is the best path and the best procedure to execute the Uniform Civil Code.

Conservative Hindus have different concerns regarding the Uniform Civil Code. Their thought process is, that Hindus already sacrificed much of their ancient traditions and customs because of the Hindu Code bills, If the Uniform Civil Code get executed with a new avatar, then the Hindu religion might sacrifice more than anybody as they already suffered in the 1950s. Their concern is half-baked because Hindus sacrifice nothing. Hindus removed and demolished the age-old traditions which are inhuman and cruel. Monogamy, succession acts, and maintenance rights gave rights to women which uplifted the lifestyle of Hindu women. Their concern might be of some importance because pluralism in Hinduism should not get washed away in the haste of executing the Uniform Civil Code. The traditions that are harmless and create no discrimination should not be touched in Hinduism as well as in any religion.

Conclusion

The Uniform Civil Code can be executed by having a separate uniform law for every religion. For example Hindu Code bills. Remove the discriminatory traditions and customs and have uniform codes that should be applicable to that religious community across India.

The reformation of the personal laws in the Muslim community is possible, that too constitutionally by the correct interpretation of Article 25, 25(1), 25(2).

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